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GOOD PRACTICES & RESEARCH INNOVATION COLLECTED - BBF

ADVISOR NETWORK FOR OPTIMAL FERTILISERS USE

Practice BBF n° 1

USING AND RETAINING CROP RESIDUES

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, mineralization, crop residues

#Crop residues, such as sugar beet leaves, can leave significant amounts of nutrients (e.g., 50 kg N/ha) in the soil after harvest.

Nutrient mineralization from residues supports soil organisms and subsequent crops but is often overlooked in fertilization strategies.

Quantifying nutrient release helps optimize fertilization strategies, reducing runoff and maximizing resource use.

Short description

➔ Depending on the crop, crop residues can contain considerable amounts of nutrients. The nutrients are for instance stored in leaves, which are after being harvested left on the field. When degrading, those nutrients become available for soil organisms and the following crop. For instance the crop residues of sugar beets, a commonly grown crop in the Netherlands, leave over 50 kg N per hectare on the field after being harvested. However, those nutrients are often not considered when creating a fertilization strategy. The additional mineralized nutrients are prone to runoff. This research innovation quantifies the mineralization of nutrients out of crop residues and considers those during the following year in order to make a fertilization strategy that considers all the available nutrients, not only those applied but also the ones that become available in the soil throughout the year.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Depends on the crop. This can often be a basic fertilization with slurry with an additional artificial fertilizer.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The mineralization rate is uncertain, as it depends on many factors such as tillage intensity and weather circumstances.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Depending on the strategy. Taking samples would take a few hours per month, basing the numbers on literature hours per year.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** broadcasting

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** None
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather high
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** abundantly available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** abundantly available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** Depends on crop
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** higher
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** higher
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** higher
- **All materials present in the BBF:** agricultural residues
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** The BBF is available for a multitude of cultivation techniques. However, the application depends on the machinery applied. The degradation rate depends on the tillage depth and crop residues will also be affect the sowing/planting process.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre
- **Influence on soil quality:** No, although considering the mineralization rate of crop residues might alter the fertilization strategy, which on the long term affects soil quality.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** none
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** None
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** No
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**
 - N: decrease, as the available nutrients are used more efficiently preventing an overapplication
 - P: decrease, as the available nutrients are used more efficiently preventing an

- overapplication
- K: decrease, as the available nutrients are used more efficiently preventing an overapplication
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** none
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** No

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information:

Wageningen Research

Contact information of the FIN partner: ardy.saarloos@wur.nl

Eu member state: The Netherlands

Find out more

Source of information: Wageningen University & Research

Additional info/links:

<https://www.handboekbodembemesting.nl/nl/handboekbodembemesting/ingangen/handeling/organische-stofbeheer/organische-stofbalans/kengetallen-organische-stof.htm>

Practice BBF n° 2

CUT&CARRY FERTILIZERS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, plant-based fertilizers, organic matter

#Cut-and-carry fertilizers are plant-based fertilizers, often made from legumes, grown on less fertile land and transported to other fields.

Cut-and-carry fertilizers reduce reliance on animal or synthetic inputs, enhance soil structure, and add organic matter.

Downsides include high land use and transport costs due to low nutrient density.

Short description

- Cut and carry fertilizers are organic fertilizers produced from plants. Those plants are often leguminous species. The plants are grown in one place and after being harvested transported to another location and applied as fertilizers. In between they might be dried and processed into grains. The growing of the fertilizing crops is often done on less arable fields. Once they are mature, they are brought to agricultural areas where they can contribute to soil fertility.
- Such a cropping system can result in plant-based fertilization strategies that reduce the need of animal or artificial fertilizers. The production and application lead to less direct greenhouse gas emissions. By adding considerable amounts of organic matter, the fertilization strategy can contribute to enhancing the soil structure, supporting soil life and if applied in the form a mulch layer plant-based fertilizers can reduce weed pressure.
- A downside of this technique is the land requirements, as external land is required for the mineral input in other regions. Therefore, less fertile soils are often used for this method. Additionally, the approach can be costly as it requires additional land and transporting materials that have a relatively low nutrient density.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Depends on the crop. This can often be a basic fertilization with slurry with an additional artificial fertilizer.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Fertilization strategies are often based on the application of mineral fertilizers. Also the application of slurry, which comes from animals, is often based on grass that was fertilized with mineral fertilizers. To reduce the dependency on mineral fertilizers, cut & carry fertilizers can be applied.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Multiple years, as you need time for the nutritional crops to grow and develop.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** broadcasting

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Yes, as the fertilizers have a low nutrient density, mowing and transporting is one of the largest challenges.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** somewhat low
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** somewhat low

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** Depends on the crop harvested
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** Depends on the crop harvested
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** lower
- **All materials present in the BBF:** plant extracts
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes, an increase in organic matter and potentially an alternation in soil life.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment, transportation, storage
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Increase in soil life, less greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Arguably, it could also be used as fodder

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** No

- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** yes
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**
 - N: As it is a slow fertilizer, it might increase. This can be reduced with a good fertilization strategy.
 - P: As it is a slow fertilizer, it might increase. This can be reduced with a good fertilization strategy.
 - K: As it is a slow fertilizer, it might increase. This can be reduced with a good fertilization strategy.
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** substantial
- **All features of the BBF which may hinder its social acceptance:** logistics
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** moderate increase
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** No

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: WUR
Contact information of the FIN partner: ardy.saarloos@wur.nl
Eu member state: The Netherlands

Find out more

Additional info/links:

https://www.louisbolk.nl/sites/default/files/publication/pdf/overzichtsdokument-maaimeststoffen-overview-cutcarry-fertilizers-ubersichtsdokument_0.pdf

Practice BBF n° 3

PIG SLURRY COMPOSITION ANALYSIS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, Spain, nutrient analysis, pig slurry

#Pig slurry contains valuable nutrients but without analysis it the nutrient content is uncertain

Analyzing slurry composition allows for precise adjustments in mineral fertilization strategies reducing the risk of under- or over-fertilization.

Over-fertilization increases environmental risks, while under-fertilization can limit crop yield potential

INFORME ANALITICO N° E23/00938

Cliete: INTIA
Entregado por: Avda. Serapio Huidi 22 (31010) Villava -Navarra

Cod. Muestra: E23/00877

Fecha de recepción: 27/06/2023
Fecha de inicio de análisis: 27/06/2023
Fecha final de análisis: 26/10/2023

Referencia: FE-24-050 Purin cerdo fondo
Tipo de Muestra: Fertilizantes Organicos

Descripción de la muestra
Fertilizantes Organicos

Análisis realizados:

Determinación	Resultado	Técnica analítica	Método
Materia Seca	1,52 %	15,24 kg/T	Gravimetría PT005
Cobre	77,0 mg Cu/kg sms	1,17 g Cu/T	ICP-MS PT151
pH	7,47		Potenciometría/Kjeldahl PT040 *
Nitrógeno total	3,49 % N sms	0,53 kg N/T	Kjeldahl PT190
Fósforo (P2O5)	5,39 % P2O5 sms	0,82 kg P2O5/T	ICP-MS PT020 *
Potasio (K2O)	1,36 % K2O sms	0,21 kg K2O/T	ICP-MS PT020 *
Zinc	540 mg Zn/kg sms	8,23 g Zn/T	ICP-MS PT151
Cadmio	0,453 mg Cd/kg sms	0,01 g Cd/T	ICP-MS PT151
Cromo	36,2 mg Cr/kg sms	0,55 g Cr/T	ICP-MS PT151
Níquel	15,5 mg Ni/kg sms	0,24 g Ni/T	ICP-MS PT151
Piomo	3,40 mg Pb/kg sms	0,05 g Pb/T	ICP-MS PT151
Mercurio	0,0217 mg Hg/kg sms	0,33 mg Hg/T	EAA PT022
C. Eléctrica (1:5)	1,55 dS/m		Potenciometría/Kjeldahl PT040 *
Nitrógeno Amoniacal	1,88 %N-NH4 sms	0,29 kg N-NH4/T	Potenciometría/Kjeldahl PT040 *
Materia Orgánica	69,9 % sms	10,50 kg/T	Cálculo PT006C *

Observaciones

Short description

➔ Since 2022, it is mandatory in Spain to have a recent product analysis when applying organic fertilizers. However, this is not yet a common practice among farmers. Pig slurry, as a widely used organic fertilizer, play an important role in the fertilization strategy of many farmers. Understanding the nutrient content of pig slurry is important for the nutrient management. However, without knowing

a nutrient analysis it is not possible to know the nutrient content of the slurry. This increases the risk of either over or underfertilizing the field. Underfertilizing the crop might prevent the crop reaching its yield potential. Yet, overfertilizing might result in negative externalities due to environmental risks. By analysing the composition of pig slurry, farmers can adjust their mineral fertilization strategies more accurately and adjust the artificial fertilizer gift accordingly.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? As nitrogen fertilizer the standard in the region is Urea 46%

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? When trying to adjust or reduce nitrogen fertilization, it is important to know beforehand the amount of nitrogen we will apply when using a specific organic product.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** liquid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** band placement

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** abundantly available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** abundantly available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** no
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:**
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:**
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** similar
- **All materials present in the BBF:** animal manure
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes, taking into account the amount of nitrogen applied with pig slurry, we can reduce mineral nitrogen fertilization and then, N losses to the environment.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Soil organic matter, reduce N losses...
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** No
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** Can contain heavy metals...
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** It depends
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**
 - Nitrogen: similar
 - Phosphorus: none
 - Potassium: none
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** yes: nitrous oxide, yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **All features of the BBF which may hinder its social acceptance:** odor
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** moderate increase
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, leading to a reduction of mineral fertilizers

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: INTIA

Contact information of the FIN partner: pecharte@intiasa.es

Eu member state: Spain

Practice BBF n° 4

MANAGING NUTRIENT AVAILABILITY RATE FROM MUNICIPAL SLUDGE

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, Spain, municipal sludge, nitrogen availability

#Municipal sludge has a stable nutrient composition, enabling precise fertilization adjustments.

Applying municipal sludge as a stable and cost-effective organic fertilizer to minimize the need for mineral fertilizers

Farmers can reduce mineral nitrogen application by incorporating sludge into their strategies.

TIPO DE FERTILIZANTE ORGÁNICO	ÉPOCA DE REPARTO	
	Verano-otoño	Invierno-primavera
A	0.20	0.30
B	0.25	0.40
C	0.30	0.50

Tipo de producto:
 A: Estiércol de vacuno, de ovino, de caprino, de caballar, compost, fracción sólida de digerido, lodo de EDAR.
 B: Purín de vacuno, de ovino, de caprino, de caballar, estiércol de cerdos, de conejo, de aves rico en cama, fracción líquida del digerido.
 C: Purín de cerdos, de aves, estiércol de aves pobre en cama.

Short description

➔ Municipal sludge is a large source of nutrients. Unlike other organic fertilizers, municipal sludge has a stable composition, enabling precise adjustments to mineral fertilization. Nitrogen in organic fertilizer is available in different ways and depending on which one is prevailing, products need to be managed in one or another way. For years field trials with these products have been developed, leading to a better understanding of the nitrogen availability during years after application. The aim is to raise awareness among farmers about reducing mineral nitrogen fertilization when using municipal sludge.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Nitrogen: Urea 46%

- Phosphorus: TSP 45%
- Potassium: KCl 60%, but it is not applied to cereals in our region as soil has high potassium contents

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?
 Farmers usually apply municipal sludge in our region as it is a cheap fertilizer (they don't pay for it), but most of them are not aware of the amount of mineral N they can save when applying this product.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** broadcasting

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** sufficiently available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** sufficiently available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:**
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:**
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** lower
- **All materials present in the BBF:** municipal sludge
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes, it increases organic matter content and lead to a reduction of mineral N application.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Reducing mineral fertilizers use.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** No

- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** Heavy metals
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**
 - N: decrease
 - P: none
 - K: none
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** Yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** moderate increase
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, it will lead to a reduction of N losses to the environment, and it is also a way of recycling nutrients.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: INTIA
Contact information of the FIN partner: pecharte@intiasa.es
Eu member state: Spain

Find out more

Source of information: Own experimentation

Practice BBF n° 5

SCRUBBING OF STABLE AIR TO PRODUCE AMMONIUM SULPHATE

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, Belgium, air scrubbing, ammonium

#Air scrubbing systems recover ammonia from livestock housing and create a washwater

The washwater can be used as a recuperated fertilizer

Best applied close to roots and at the start of the growing season for nitrogen efficiency.

Short description

➔ Emissions of NH_3 from livestock housing and slurry storage represent a large part of the total NH_3 emissions from agricultural activities. Therefore chemical air scrubbing is used to reduce the ammonia and odor components in stable air. Water with added sulfuric acid is used to stream along the filter package. The acid washwater reacts with the ammonia in the stable air, producing ammonium sulphate which remains in the washwater. To optimally work the washwater needs to be removed regularly. This washwater can be used as a recuperated fertilizer and is recognized as a substitute for synthetic fertilizer. The resulting fertiliser is liquid and can be applied as any other liquid fertilizer through injection or through spraying followed by immediate ploughing. Applications where the fertiliser is brought as close as possible to the roots is ideal. This fertiliser is best applied at the

start of the growing season because the N in the product is present as ammonium and it still needs to be converted to nitrate before the plant can absorb it. This type of fertiliser is useful for any kind of crop, but in case a S containing counter acid is used in the production step the resulting fertiliser can be of particular interest for crops that also have a sulfur need such as cabbage crops, onions, celery, grains, sugar beets etc.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Mineral fertilizer and/or pig manure

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The need to reduce emissions from stable air.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Need for permits + regular monitoring + obligatory analyses on frequent basis.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** liquid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** band placement

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** substantial
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** The washwater has an acid PH and is thus corrosive, therefore storage tanks should be made from non-corrosive material. Also at all times it should be avoided that organic manure comes in contact with this water as toxic H₂S can be formed. People that manipulate the BBF should have a clear view on the potential chemical dangers when transporting/storing the BBF.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** abundantly available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** somewhat low

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** no
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** (4-8)-0-0
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** 0:(4-8)
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** similar
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** lower
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Applicable to a multitude of cultivation techniques, although less suitable for foliar application.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** As the fertilizer had an acidic pH one should consider the buffer capacity of the soil + this type of fertilizer is also rich in S, this element has an optimum for fertilisation.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty

- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment, storage
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Total N is present in mineral form and can thus be a good replacement for synthetic fertilizers => closing the cycle.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** yes, no other application

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** This product is recognized as mineral fertilizer and does not fall under the Nitrates Directive as animal manure when used. Important when mixed with animal manure it is again categorized as animal manure. However, this is strongly discouraged for the risk of H₂S formation.
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** No, as for the moment the BBF is considered to origin from intensive pig production
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

The product only contains nitrogen, the product shows similar N leaching patterns as compared to classical fertilization

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** substantial
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** moderate increase
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, as it could help in the image of agriculture, by contributing to a more circular economy (nutrient recuperation and avoiding mineral fertilizer use from fossil resources).
- **Any relevant information or remarks about the above can be added here:** The BBF is particularly useful for demanding crops

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: Ugent
Contact information of the FIN partner: evi.michels@ugent.be
Eu member state: Belgium

Find out more

Source of information: EMIS/VITO and Nutricycle Vlaanderen

Additional info/links:

<https://nutricycle.vlaanderen/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/Brochure-Ammoniumsulfaat.pdf.pdf>

UGhent Biobased Fertilizer: GP: Scrubbing of stable air to produce ammonium sulphate

Source: Nutricycle Vlaanderen, brochure ammonium sulphate

Practice BBF n° 6

STRIPPING-SCRUBBING OF LIQUID FRACTION OF PIG MANURE TO PRODUCE AMMONIUM NITRATE

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, Belgium, stripping-scrubbing, ammonium nitrate

#Stripping-scrubbing converts ammonia from pig manure into ammonium nitrate, a liquid biobased fertilizer.

This can be achieved at farm level and reduce farm emissions.

This fertilizer can be applied on the field based on the requirements of the crop.

Short description

- ➔ Stripping-scrubbing of the liquid fraction of pig manure allows for on farm production of biobased fertilizer. It starts with the liquid fraction of pig manure followed by scrubbing for ammonium salt recuperation.
- ➔ The operating principle of stripping-scrubbing is that ammonia (NH₃) is stripped by air, steam or vacuum through the nitrogen rich waste stream in an NH₃ stripping reactor, resulting in NH₃ transfer from the aqueous phase to a gas phase. The released NH₃ is removed in a chemical air scrubber by washing it with a strong acidic solution such as nitric acid (HNO₃), resulting in ammonium nitrate. The efficiency of process can be increased by adjusting the pH and/or temperature by which more of water soluble NH₄-N ion will be converted into the gaseous ammonia.
- ➔ The resulting fertiliser is liquid and can be applied as any other liquid fertilizer through injection or through spraying followed by immediate ploughing. Applications where the fertiliser is brought as close as possible to the roots is ideal. This fertiliser is best applied at the start of the growing season because the nitrogen in the product is present as ammonium and it still needs to be converted to nitrate before the plant can absorb it. This type of fertiliser is useful for any kind of crop, but in case a S containing counter acid is used in the production step the resulting fertiliser can be of particular interest for crops that also have a sulfur need such as cabbage crops, onions, celery, grains, sugar beets etc.
- ➔ As this fertiliser has an acidic character special attention should be paid to the material use when applying this fertiliser. Also, at any time the mixture with animal manure should be avoided as toxic H₂S formation could occur.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Mineral fertilizer and/or (pig) manure (slurry)

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** liquid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** band placement

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** average
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Corrosion hazard for storage tanks etc + attention for processing acid solutions.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** very low
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** very low

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** no
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** 15-0-0
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** 0:15
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** similar
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** lower
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Multitude, less suitable for foliar application. Advised is band placement with injection, no broadcasting.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial, ornamental
- **Influence on soil quality:** Low pH product, so attention is needed for the buffer capacity of the soil, compensation with liming can be needed when the pH is influenced. S dosage must be in line with crop request.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment, storage
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Total N is present in mineral form and can thus be a good replacement for synthetic fossil-based fertilizers while at the same time excess manure/digestate can be processed and valorised => closing the circle.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** Currently the use of this product falls under the Nitrates Directive as animal manure (max 170 kg N/ha) and not as mineral N. Most mineral salts do comply with the Renure criteria
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** No, as for the moment the manure/liquid fraction is considered to origin from intensive pig production
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

The product only contains nitrogen, the product shows similar patterns as compared to classical fertilization

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** moderate increase
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, as it could help in the image of agriculture, by contributing to a more circular economy.
- **Any relevant information or remarks about the above can be added here:** Moderate increase in workload for the farmer as long as there is no RENURE status, after that it can replace the time spent on spreading mineral fertilizer

For now, the focus was on ammonium nitrate but by varying with the counter acid in the washing step also ammonium sulphate can be produced which can be very useful in cultivation of certain crops.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information:

Ugent

Contact information of the FIN partner: evi.michels@ugent.be

Eu member state: Belgium

Find out more

Source of information: H2020 Fertimanure / Interreg Nitroman

Additional info/links:

<https://www.fertimanure.eu/en/news/consult/54>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zhHmOtXkSOo>

Practice BBF n° 7

GUARANTEED LEVEL OF NUTRIENTS MANURE PRODUCTS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, nutrient levels, precision fertilization

#Nutrient analysis of animal manure allows precise application based on crop and soil needs.

On-farm measurement equipment and NIR technology can ensure nutrient consistency before application.

Accurate analysis reduces reliance on synthetic fertilizers and optimizes nutrient use efficiency.

Short description

- ➔ To ensure optimal nutrient use, it is important to guarantee the nutrient levels in animal manure before application. This approach is especially relevant for slurry and other processed forms of biobased fertilizers. By precisely determining the nutrient composition, farmers can supply nutrients based on the crop and soil need. This is currently not the case due to reliance on assumed nutrient values. This practice applies to all crops where animal manure is used.
- ➔ Farmers often turn to artificial fertilizers to make specific adjustments in nitrogen or phosphate levels. However, with guaranteed nutrient levels in animal manure, these adjustments can also be made using manure, reducing reliance on synthetic fertilizers. Achieving this requires on-farm measurement equipment capable of providing fast and accurate nutrient analysis directly in the manure storage. Before application, an additional measurement should be taken by the arable farmer, for example using near-infrared (NIR) technology. More information about this can be found in the precision farming GP about NIR.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Organic manure (assumed nutrients) & artificial manure

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The challenge: the animal manure space is not used to its potential. In the ideal world the use of artificial fertilizer will be very much limited. To manage this, nutrient levels of animal manure should be known, so the animal manure space can be used to its full potential.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** liquid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** drip irrigation

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Nutrient results should be known before applying, allowing some time to adjust the fertilizer plan.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** very low
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** very low

Agronomical traits

- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** Will be known if can be measure (= this RI)
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** Will be known if can be measure (= this RI)
- **All materials present in the BBF:** animal manure
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Not yet but we need multiple cultivations techniques which will be suitable for the use of the different manure fractions.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental
- **Influence on soil quality:** Improved organic matter and improved usage of nutrients.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, silty, chalky
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** pesticides; mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Circular agriculture.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Most likely yes

Administrative context

- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** Yes, the maximum space to use animal manure is limited by policies.
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes, if the manure is organic.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

Much lower for all.

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** substantial
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** none
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, increasing circular agriculture. More healthy growing plants with less artificial fertilizers.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: ZLTO
Contact information of the FIN partner: Peter.paree@zltto.nl
Eu member state: The Netherlands

Find out more

Source of information: Wageningen University, part of "Bemest op z'n best"

Practice BBF n° 8

AGRICYCLING: REGIONAL USAGE

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, compost, residual streams

#Reusing societal residual streams as compost for agricultural use.

Data-driven analysis ensures nutrients meet soil and crop needs, optimizing fertilizer use.

Lowering fertilizer costs, enhancing soil fertility, and creating a sustainable link between urban waste and agriculture.

Short description

→ This good practice is inspired by a collaboration between farmers with a partnership with governments, and nature organizations called Agricycling. However, the initiative can be applied in many other places. It focuses on reusing available residual streams from society, such as roadside grass, by delivering them directly to farmers for composting. This process optimizes the use of residual streams from a soil perspective and uses the streams based on what the soil and plant needs. This can serve as an addition to or replacement for existing fertilization. The application process is data-driven and begins with analyzing the residual streams to assess their mineral composition and organic matter content. Based on this analysis, decisions are made about how to distribute the compost across farms. At the farm level, a soil analysis determines the specific application, ensuring it is done at the right time and place and in line with the needs of the soil and crops. This tailored approach provides to a sustainable alternative or addition to traditional fertilization, strengthening the connection between urban waste management and agricultural productivity. This results in both economic and ecological benefits, as it reduces fertilizer costs, while increasing soil fertility and reducing the need of mineral fertilizers.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Animal based fertilizer and chemical fertilizers

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

<https://www.agricycling.nl/proces>

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: At least one year, to get all parties involved and aligned, quality protocols in place and have the practice starting.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** broadcasting

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** average
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Yes, as bio "waste" from municipalities, Water boards, and nature organizations has to be transported to the different farms. Quality samples have to be taken and analysed before the compost can be applied.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather high
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** sufficiently available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** sufficiently available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** Will be known (measured) before applying compost
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** Will be known (measured) before applying compost
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** similar
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** similar
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** similar
- **All materials present in the BBF:** compost
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes, specific cultivation techniques, depends on kind of cultivation.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre
- **Influence on soil quality:** Improved by maintaining organic matter.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** fuel, transportation, storage, quality measurements
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** improved soil quality, leading to more consistent healthy production. Leading to higher profitability. Indirect effect: "waste" is turned into useful components instead of burned to produce energy.

Administrative context

- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** Yes, there are policies in place to control the production of compost and compost complies to the common ammonia and phosphate regulation.
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Unknown, probably depending on the source.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

Lower, healthy soil can contain nutrients much better.

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** moderate increase
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, bio-waste from the municipality is used to produce food.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: ZLTO

Contact information of the FIN partner: peter.paree@zlto.nl

Eu member state: The Netherlands

Find out more

Additional info/links:

<https://www.agricyding.nl/proces>

<https://www.agricyding.nl>

Practice BBF n° 9

SOLID FRACTION OF A DIGESTATE FROM PLANT MATERIAL

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, digestates, methanization

#Digestates, a by-product of methanization, are rich in organic and mineral nutrients for fertilization.

Spreading digestates improves nutrient efficiency and reduces methane emissions from manure storage.

Local anaerobic digestion supports renewable energy generation and sustainable fertilization practices.

Short description

➔ Digestates are the majority by-product of methanization. They are rich in organic and mineral elements, giving them a high organic fertilizer potential. The spreading of digestates, particularly of agricultural origin, is the most commonly carried out practice in order to valorize this product. Physicochemical and agronomic indicators are used in order to quantify their characteristics and qualities. The characteristics of digestates are very variable and depend on several factors such as inputs, operating conditions of methanizers and post-treatments. Here we propose the solid fraction of a digestate, mainly from plant matter, and supplemented with non-ruminant slurry and ruminant slurry.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Green waste compost

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The methanization sector has been developing rapidly in France for about ten years. This sector meets the needs of waste treatment, increased energy autonomy and energy decarbonization. But it also provides positive externalities, digestate. For the agricultural world, digestate is now considered a real product. It provides farmers who use it with a real technical and economic benefit. It also represents considerable potential for savings on synthetic nitrogen fertilizers.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: In order to optimally use digestates, the first step is to know the products that will be spread. Indeed, digestates

vary greatly depending on the method of methanization (dry or wet), the inputs and the post-treatments applied. The principle of fertilization balance, applicable to all fertilizers, also applies to digestates. The objective is to ensure that the crop's needs are covered by the soil and by digestates. With this in mind, calculation methods exist and are accessible for example on the site <https://fertiliser-avec-des-digestats.fr/>

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** broadcasting

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** substantial
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Emissions during digestate storage depend on the type of inputs, the residence time of the material in digestion and the storage temperature. Good practices must therefore be implemented to limit GHG emissions during digestate storage, such as covering digestate storage structures with a gas-tight cover, and recovering the residual biogas, which can be recovered. Or, to limit N₂O and NH₃ emissions, install a crust, a natural floating layer, or a non-watertight cover (in accordance with the ICPE 2021 rules, covers are not mandatory in the case of lagoons if a residence time of 80 days of digestion upstream can be justified).
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** abundantly available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** sufficiently available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** "N tot =8-17 kg/tMB - P₂O₅ = 21-32 kg/tMB - K₂O= 8-13 kg/t MB"
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** 11-17
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** similar
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** higher
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** higher
- **All materials present in the BBF:** digestate
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?**
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Depending on their dry matter content and the form of the carbon they contain, digestates modify, like all other organic fertilizers, in comparison with a control without fertilization or with mineral fertilization: the stable organic matter content of the soil, which, due to its lower density than the mineral phase of the soil, contributes by dilution to reduce the apparent density of the soil and therefore the compaction of the soil, and to increase the porosity of the soil; the activity of earthworm communities (as well as the composition of these communities) which, by modifying the clay-humic complex, but also by creating galleries and producing worm castings, contribute to an improvement in the infiltration of water into the soil and structural stability; the activity of microorganisms which, by consuming the labile carbon in

the digestate, produce a variety of molecules (microbial metabolites) which either increase the cohesion between particles and aggregates (this is the case of polysaccharides) or reduce the wettability of aggregates (this is the case of hydrophobic molecules), and consequently improve the structural stability of the soil. However, the reduction in the wettability of aggregates can lead to a reduction in the water retention capacity of the soil; this can be detrimental, particularly in the case of sandy soils.

- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** storage, equipment
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Most of the benefits of digestate application concern soil fertility.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** If the methanization unit integrates urban sewage sludge, the spreading must also comply with additional constraints specified in the decree of January 8, 1998 (three-year rotation of spreading, thresholds to be respected for the contributions of trace metal elements per hectare and cumulative flows of trace metal elements over 10 years).
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** Digestates may contain metallic trace elements on the inputs used in the composition of the digestate and their proportion (B, Cd, Cu, Mo, Zn, even Ag and Hg for digestates based on inputs such as urban sludge and household waste). It should be noted that in France, concentrations in spread products are subject to regulations.
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Methanation digestates can be used in Organic Agriculture (AB) unless the incoming materials consist of sewage treatment plant sludge and/or from the agri-food industries. The regulations govern this specific agronomic valorization. Bibliographic data and field feedback show that digestates play an interesting role for farms run in organic agriculture showing synergies between methanization and AB.
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

Risks of nitrate loss through leaching are possible if digestates are used inappropriately. The choice of application period depends on the nitrogen requirements of the crops, the nitrogen content of the product to be applied and the technical possibilities for spreading. Excessive inputs are likely to be lost through leaching during the autumn-winter period. For the same input dose of crude, the “Solid fraction - majority non-ruminant manure” digestates, as well as “Crude or liquid fraction - other situations including majority vegetable” and “Crude or liquid fraction - majority non-ruminant manure” stand out slightly from all digestates, with a slightly larger pool of volatilizable nitrogen.

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** yes: nitrous oxide, yes:

ammonia

- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **All features of the BBF which may hinder its social acceptance:** odor
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** none
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Methanization currently has a rather negative image in France, which may call into question the use of digestates. The main issue is competition between food crops and energy crops.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: AC3A

Contact information of the FIN partner: melisande.nardy@na.chambagri.fr

Eu member state: France

Find out more

Source of information: A range of information on digestates is available on the FertiDig project website (<https://fertiliser-avec-des-digestats.fr/>).

Practice BBF n° 10

USE OF DIGESTATE ORIGINATING FROM SMALL SCALE FARM DIGESTION

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, Belgium, anaerobic digestion, digestate

#Small scale anaerobic digestion on dairy farms generates biogas while producing digestate as a fertilizer

The process captures methane emissions from manure storage, reducing the farm's carbon footprint and creating a renewable energy source

Digestate improves nutrient availability and efficiency, making it an environmentally friendly alternative to traditional manure

Short description

→ Small-scale anaerobic digestion of residual flows (mainly at dairy farms) can help the farmer to fulfil the electricity needs of the farm and partly the heat demand through combustion of biogas in a combined heat and power unit. It has a local character and limited scale as compared to a larger digester. As a “waste stream” the resulting digestate can be used as a fertilizer. It can be used and spread in a similar way as classic manure but has environmental advantages. Under default practices animal production causes significant amounts of methane slipping from manure storage. By first putting manure in anaerobic digestion this methane slip is avoided and even captured into a renewable resource. This way the carbon footprint of (dairy) farms is reduced. Furthermore, during the AD process the nutrients from the animal manure are mineralized rendering them more plant available and thus increasing their nutrient use efficiency.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? Mineral fertilizer and/or pig manure (slurry)

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** liquid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** band placement

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Not really, most of the time the digestate is stored in a separate storage.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** very low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** abundantly available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** sufficiently available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** no
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** 3-1.5-1
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** 15-20:1
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** higher
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** similar
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** similar
- **All materials present in the BBF:** digestate
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Use of digestate can increase the organic matter in soil. Biostimulating properties have been described but this not fully clear yet.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** storage
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** none
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Reduced carbon footprint of nutrient management. Improved soil quality compared to only mineral fertilizer use.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes, if not used as a fertilizer the digestate is considered a waste stream.

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** Currently, the digestate is still considered manure and falls under the Nitrates Directive
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

Similar patterns can be expected as classic fertilisation with manure

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** substantial
- **All features of the BBF which may hinder its social acceptance:** odor

- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** none
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** It is a manure processing step which might be seen as positive in frame of optimal nutrient management.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information:

University Ghent

Contact information of the FIN partner: evi.michels@Ugent.be

Eu member state: Belgium

Find out more

Source of information: Pocket Power, Nutri2Cycle, own research and pilots

Practice BBF n° 11

OPTIMIZING FERTILIZATION BY USING NON-MICROBIAL BIOSTIMULANTS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, biostimulants, nutrient efficiency

#Biostimulants enhance nutrient uptake efficiency, tolerance to abiotic stress, and soil health.

Biostimulants are made from natural sources like plant extracts, microbes, and animal byproducts, and often applied preventively.

Their use can reduce reliance on synthetic fertilizers by improving plant nutrient efficiency

Short description

➔ Biostimulants aim to improve the effectiveness of fertilization, the efficiency of plant nutrition. Their use is rather preventive. A plant biostimulant is a product that stimulates plant nutrition processes independently of the nutrients it contains, with the sole aim of improving one or more of the following characteristics of plants or their rhizosphere: a) nutrient use efficiency; b) tolerance to abiotic stress; c) qualitative characteristics; d) availability of nutrients confined in the soil and rhizosphere. The biostimulants are made from a variety of natural sources, including plant extracts, microbial cultures and animal byproducts. They can be processed in different ways, by for instance being fermented, which are then formulated into products that can be applied on the fields.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? This practice can be compared to fertilization without the use of biostimulants, since the aim of this BBF is to optimize conventional fertilization.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? 1. Nutrient Use Efficiency and Fertilizer Management Challenges:

Challenge: One of the main on-farm challenges is optimizing the use of chemical fertilizers. Over-fertilization can lead to nutrient imbalances, environmental pollution (e.g., water contamination), and inefficient nutrient uptake by plants. Farmers face growing pressure to reduce fertilizer use while maintaining or even improving crop yields.

Opportunity: Biostimulants improve the efficiency of nutrient uptake by plants, enabling them to use

available nutrients more effectively, even in soils with suboptimal fertility. By enhancing nutrient use efficiency, biostimulants help reduce the need for chemical fertilizers, lowering costs and environmental impacts.

2. Abiotic Stress and Climate Variability:

Challenge: Farmers are increasingly dealing with climate change-related stresses, such as drought, heatwaves, and flooding, which reduce crop resilience and productivity. Crops that are stressed by extreme weather conditions often show reduced nutrient uptake and growth.

Opportunity: Biostimulants have been found to enhance plant tolerance to abiotic stress by improving cellular functions, promoting root growth, and boosting plant defence mechanisms. For instance, some biostimulants help plants cope with water scarcity by increasing root depth and efficiency, which is crucial in drought-prone areas.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: 1 or 2 years

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** liquid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** foliar feeding

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** very low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** sufficiently available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** somewhat low

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** no
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:**
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:**
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** lower
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** lower
- **All materials present in the BBF:** digestate, compost, biochar, algae, plant extracts
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed
- **Influence on soil quality:** There may be some, but this is not the primary objective of the biostimulant.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** silty, chalky, loamy, clay, sandy, peaty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** none
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Improved Soil Health.

Enhanced Microbial Activity: Biostimulants, particularly those containing microbial inoculants, foster beneficial soil microbes, enhancing nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition.

Increased Organic Matter: Regular application promotes carbon sequestration and improves soil structure over time.

- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** Not in UE
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

It can have an impact because it improves root growth and therefore root capacity to retain nutrients.

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **All features of the BBF which may hinder its social acceptance:** odor
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** none
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** No. It's not public knowledge.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: AC3A
Contact information of the FIN partner: melisande.nardy@na.chambargi.fr
Eu member state: France

Find out more

Source of information: Organizations and Associations:

European Biostimulants Industry Council (EBIC): A leading organization in the regulation and promotion of biostimulants in Europe. EBIC provides detailed reports and guidelines on the use and regulation of biostimulants.

EBIC Website: <https://biostimulants.eu/>

Additional info/links:

Practical Sources:

"Fertilizing Sustainably with Biostimulants"

Author: Institut Technique de l'Agriculture Biologique (ITAB)

Summary: This practical guide offers information on the use of biostimulants in agricultural systems, with a focus on organic farming. It also presents case studies on the effectiveness of biostimulants to improve fertilizer efficiency and increase plant stress resistance.

Source: ITAB, official website.

"Use of Biostimulants in Vegetable and Fruit Crops"

Author: Chambre d'Agriculture

Summary: This technical document from the Chambre d'Agriculture in France provides practical information on using biostimulants in intensive crops, particularly vegetables and fruits. It includes case studies and testimonials from farmers.

Source: Chambre d'Agriculture, official website.

"Biostimulants in Agricultural Production"

Author: INRA (National Institute of Agronomic Research)

Summary: This publication presents research results on biostimulants, focusing on their long-term effects on crop yields and optimizing fertilizer use.

Source: INRA, scientific and technical publication.

Practice BBF n° 12

THE USE OF BIOCHAR IN GROWING MEDIA FOR SOILLESS CULTIVATION IN HORTICULTURE

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, Belgium, biochar, growing media

#In horticulture growing media are often used, which can contribute from organic additions

Biochar can be added to growing media as a sustainable alternative to peat, improving plant growth, disease suppression, and nutrient availability

Produced via pyrolysis of biomass, biochar contains nutrients and can adjust the pH of the growing media to enhance nutrient mobility

Short description

- ➔ Growing media include any materials other than soil used as a horticultural substrate for plant rooting and cultivation in a confined volume, as part of controlled environment agriculture. These growing media are used for growing vegetables, fruits and ornamentals in a range of hydroponic systems in greenhouses. Peat is widely used as major constituent in growing media but is controversial due to damage to peatlands and greenhouse gas emissions at harvesting.
- ➔ Biochar can be used in growing media blends as fertilizer or for improving plant growth, disease suppression, and as a sustainable (partial) replacement of peat. Biochar is one of the products of pyrolysis, i.e., heating of biomass with no or limited presence of air. It can be produced from a wide

variety of feedstocks, ranging from lignocellulosic materials (as wood, reed, and grass) to nutrient rich waste streams as manure.

- Biochar contains nutrients originating from the feedstock, which can potentially be released by use in growing media. Next to that, biochar addition can alter the pH of the growing media, which influences nutrient mobility and availability.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? In general, peat-based growing media are used.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The use of peat in growing media is getting more and more controversial due to the high environmental impact of peat harvesting from wetlands.

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** band placement

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** no logistic aspects
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** sufficiently available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** sufficiently available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** Nutrient properties of the biochar are largely determined by the nutrients present in the feedstock. A large variation can be observed.
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** Broad range depending on feedstock
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** lower
- **All materials present in the BBF:** agricultural residues, animal manure, biochar
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** The BBF focusses on the use of biochar as a replacement of peat in growing media for horticultural crops, e.g. tomato and strawberry.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes, replacing the peat (partially) by biochar will not give a one-on-one replacement.
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** growing media
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers; pesticides

- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** High potential in terms of circular use of materials and nutrients (use of renewable biomass).
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** no
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** no
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** no
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** yes
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**

no effect. The BBF is concerning the use of soilless cultivation in greenhouses, which is a closed system.

- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** substantial
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** none
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, due to a higher sustainability of the horticultural production.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: ILVO

Contact information of the FIN partner: donald.dekeyser@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

Eu member state: Belgium

Find out more

Source of information: Interreg 2 Seas project Horti-BlueC and Basta project

Additional info/links:

<https://www.horti-bluec.eu/en>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R9kB-F54Tow>

Practice BBF n° 13

FERTIBIO DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRODUCTION PROCESS OF BIO-FERTILIZERS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, biostimulants, nutrient efficiency

#The biofertilizer is composed of microorganisms like arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, bacteria, and other fungi

It is best applied after planting or in early stages to boost root interaction

The biofertilizer improves nutrient uptake efficiency, particularly phosphorus, and reduces dependency on mineral fertilizers

Short description

- The biofertilizer contains primarily of beneficial microorganisms, including arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), bacteria, and other fungi. These microorganisms are produced in vitro, in axenic cultures, and in vivo, resulting in effective inoculants. The AMF included in the biofertilizer belong to species such as *Funneliformis mosseae*, *Rhizophagus irregularis*, and *Archaeospora* spp., which have been isolated, multiplied because of their effectivity and efficiency.
- The fertilizer is delivered in the form of alginate-based capsules containing the inoculum, which includes spores, hyphae, and colonized roots, as well as phosphate-solubilizing bacteria capable of making phosphorus more accessible.
- It is suitable for use on crops such as wheat, barley, sunflower, tomato, chickpea and alfalfa. Application is most effective directly after planting or during early crop stages to maximize the interaction between the microorganisms and plant roots. The biofertilizer stimulates nutrient uptake efficiency and supports crop growth. This way, the biofertilizer can be a potential to mineral fertilizers.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? All kind of fertilizer, chemicals and organic fertilizers

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Biofertilizers, efficient in conventional agriculture, can be used effectively to reduce the use of mineral fertilizers and pesticides with a positive environmental impact on soil fertility and the diversity of agroecosystems.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: 32
 Months

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** band placement

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Develop an "industrial" production protocol for biofertilizers to be applied in Tuscan agricultural areas, including peri-urban ones, creating a high-quality supply chain.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** sufficiently available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** sufficiently available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **N-P-K composition of the BBF:** Yes
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** Yes
- **Expected availability of nitrogen (N) in the BBF:** higher
- **Expected availability of phosphorus (P) in the BBF:** higher
- **Expected availability of potassium (K) in the BBF:** higher
- **All materials present in the BBF:** micro-organisms
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes
- **Targeted crop categories:** feed, fibre, food, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes
- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** equipment
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Realization of two prototypes for the production of biofertilizers: one for the in vitro and axenic culture production of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), bacteria and other beneficial fungi and one for the production of crude inoculum (spores, hyphae, colonized roots) of AMF (homogenized and concentrated inoculum).
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** existing, however with gaps

- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** None
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** No
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**
None
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** negative: GHG emissions may increase upon using the BBF
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** time-saving
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes in this situation.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information:

Alessandra Gemmiti

Contact information of the FIN partner: alessandra.gemmiti@regione.toscana.it

+393473470365

Eu member state: Italy (Tuscany Region)

Find out more

Source of information: Data base of OG RRN

Additional info/links:

<https://fertibio.ciatoscana.eu/>

Practice BBF n° 14

BIOCHAR: INNOVATIONS THROUGH CARBONIZATIONS TESTED IN AMIATA AND MAREMMA

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bio-based fertilizers, food, GP, The Netherlands, biochar, soil fertility

#Biochar, produced of organic biomass, is used to improve soil health and add carbon to the soil

It enhances soil fertility by increasing water retention, stimulating soil life, and binding nutrients to reduce leaching

Biochar can be produced from forestry, agro-forestry, and olive-growing residues, turning waste into a valuable resource

Short description

- ➔ Biochar is a carbon-rich material produced by pyrolysis, which is the thermal decomposition in the absence of oxygen. This usually occurs in organic biomass, such as wood, agricultural residues, or other plant materials. It is primarily used as a soil amendment to improve soil health and sequester carbon. Biochar is usually applied during soil preparation and is either before or after seeding incorporated in the soil. It can be applied in combination with an organic fertilizer, like compost or slurry.
- ➔ By adding biochar to a soil, the carbon content is increased which contributes to the overall soil fertility. Specifically, the addition of biochar increases the water holding capacity of the soil. Next to that, it is a stimulus for soil life and can reduce the leaching by binding nutrients.
- ➔ The biochar can be produced of many carbon rich products. In this project the experimentation was conducted on biochar obtained from the combination of forestry, agro-forestry, olive-growing, and agriculture. In particular, the aim is to reduce the waste out of olive pruning. This is particularly interesting from a circular economy perspective which, through vegetal the production of biochar, transforms what was previously a problem into a resource.

Implementation process

Which fertiliser type is considered as the standard in this region? It depends on the cultivation and it may be chemical or organic

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Valorize waste and processing residues with less impact than other forms of disposal and at the same time generate energy and increase in the fertility of the "soil system".

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: 29 Months

Application process/mode

- **In which form is the BBF applied?** solid
- **How is the BBF applied on the field?** broadcasting

Logistics

- **Storage safety risk:** low
- **Logistic aspects to consider:** A decrease in the negative externalities of carbonization; an increase in the fertility of the "soil system"; a diversification of the forestry and agro-forestry supply chains; prototyping and development of a vertical mobile furnace with discontinuous operation capable of processing (carbonizing) ligno-cellulosic material of variable small-medium size; tests regarding possible future developments on a type of experimental small-sized pyrolytic boiler capable of operating as a pyro-gasifier for the production of syngas (i.e. flare flame) and coal; optimization, qualification and standardization of the production of biochar obtained from forestry and agricultural systems: selection of materials and mechanical preparation treatments; optimization of pyrolysis; development of mixing and packaging; monitoring of the effect of the addition of biochar on the fertility of the soil system in terms of microbiological indicators and formulation of innovative natural cosmetic/cosmeceutical lines; creation of a local synergy between the actors of the supply chain, capable of addressing the problem and attempting scientifically supported solutions.
- **Skill/education level required for safe and effective application of the BBF?** rather low
- **Availability of the BBF in this region:** sufficiently available
- **Availability of the BBF in the wider EU:** sufficiently available

Agronomical traits

- **Is it a 'slow-release' fertiliser?** yes
- **C:N ratio of the BBF:** Unknown: Biochar is mainly used to maintain soil fertility
- **All materials present in the BBF:** agricultural residues
- **Can the BBF be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, or is the use limited to one or a few techniques?** Yes, biochar on the fertility of the soil system in terms of microbiological indicators, and field evaluation in nursery, horticultural and agronomic activities; Possibility of creating a new supply chain in the territories with the involvement of new comp
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes, a decrease in the negative externalities of carbonization; an

increase in the fertility of the "soil system".

- **Soil types suitable for the BBF:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase upon using the BBF?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease upon using the BBF?** mineral or other types of fertilisers, herbicides, pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect benefits of using the BBF:** Yes, Positive effect of the addition of different types of biochar on the fertility of the soil system in terms of microbiological indicators, and field evaluation in nursery, horticultural and agronomic activities, with a clear decrease in terms of water and fertilizer use with economic advantages connected to their lower consumption.
- **Is the use as fertiliser the most valuable application of the material at hand?** Yes

Administrative context

- **Does the use of the BBF qualify for subsidies?** Yes, with RDP and other subsidies dedicated to sustainability
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the use of the BBF:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the use of the BBF?** None
- **Does the BBF contain any hazardous substances, and if this is the case, which one(s)?** None
- **Is the use of the BBF compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the use of the BBF supported by Eco-schemes?** we do not have ecoscheme for this activity
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients?**
No leaching effect
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon using the BBF?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the BBF:** little or none
- **Effects expected on the time occupation of the farmer upon using the BBF?** moderate increase
- **May the use of the BBF contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information:

Alessandra Gemmiti

Contact information of the FIN partner: alessandra.gemmiti@regione.toscana.it

Eu member state: Italy (Tuscany Region)

Find out more

Source of information: <https://www.bioactam.it/>